

MANOEUVRE

Energy System Modelling for Transition to a net-Zero 2050 for EU via
REPowerEU

Man0EUvRE – Project management plan Version 1.1, 21.05.2024

A project in the CET partnership

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List of Acronyms and Abbreviations

Table 1: List of acronyms and abbreviations

Term	Explanation
CDP	Communication and Dissemination Plan
CETP	Clean Energy Transition Partnership
DMP	Data Management Plan
ECEMF	European Climate and Energy Modelling Forum
EERA	European Energy Research Alliance
EU	European Union
IEA-ETSAP	International Energy Agency - Energy Technology Systems Analysis Program
NECP	National Energy and Climate Plan
NTNU	Norwegian University of Science and Technology
WP	Work Package
CETP	Clean Energy Transition Partnership
GA	General Assembly
MST	Management Support Team
PMP	Project Management Plan

Executive Summary

Man0EUvRE is a Clean Energy Transition Partnership 2022 project with a duration of 3 years from December 2023. The main idea of the Man0EUvRE project is to improve the framework and methodology for producing consistent national energy and climate plans across Europe. The project will do this by first developing clean energy transition scenarios towards 2050, including current policies like Fit-for-55 and REPowerEU, and the national energy and climate plans (NECPs) for the countries represented in the project. These scenarios will be used in an energy system model with a European dataset, and the outputs from the European simulation will be used as input for national or regional case studies. There are nine case studies in Man0EUvRE with different scopes. Their results will be compared with the NECP of the concerned countries or regions and fed back to the European energy system model dataset. The experience from the case studies will be used when the European energy system model dataset is updated. This will lead to learning about the clean energy transition, improve the future process of developing NECPs and align the NECPs with the European policies.

- The purpose of the Project Management Plan (PMP) is to:
- Ensure a common understanding of the project management among the partners.
- Reduce the time spent by new coworkers to familiarize themselves with the project.
- Structure and describe the management of the project.
- Facilitate high quality of the project deliverables.
- Follow and document the development of the project.

The PMP is mainly intended for internal use by project participants who have questions concerning project routines, e.g. quality assurance for deliverables, where templates can be found or how to raise an issue within the project, and for new project participants: When a project partner includes new researchers in the project, this document provides an overview of the project structure.

The PMP contains an overview of the Man0EUvRE project including its concept, objectives, timeline, governance structure and routines. It also contains a description of the content and workflow of the work packages in the project. Further, the PMP describes the quality assurance routines and risk management in the project, and the reporting procedures for the project. Finally, the PMP contains an overview of the communication and information tools and procedures in the project.

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2 Introduction

2.1 Purpose of the document

ManOEUVRE is a Clean Energy Transition Partnership 2022 project with a duration of 3 years from December 2023. ManOEUVRE is a large project consisting of many partners and modules, with a governance structure that deviates from projects that use a standard DESCA Horizon 2020[1] governance structure for large projects with 355 man months of effort. The purpose of the Project Management Plan (PMP) is to:

- Ensure a common understanding of the project management among the partners.
- Reduce the time spent by new coworkers to familiarize themselves with the project.
- Structure and describe the management of the project.
- Facilitate high quality of the project deliverables.
- Follow and document the development of the project.
- Provide all necessary information about the project procedures.

The PMP is mainly intended for internal use. This is a living document that will be updated throughout the project. The document contains links that are only working for the project participants, as they have access to the workroom where the linked documents are stored.

2.2 Structure of this document

This remaining document is structured as follows:

- Section 1: Introduction and description about the ManOEUVRE project and the document.
- Section 2: An overview of the ManOEUVRE project concept, objectives, and timeline, of the project governance structure and of the work packages.
- Section 3: The quality assurance routines used in the project.
- Section 4: Risk management in the project
- Section 5: The reporting procedures for the project
- Section 6: Communication and information tools and procedures in the project.
- Section 7: References.

2.3 Intended readership

Within the project:

- Project participants who have questions concerning project routines, e.g. quality assurance for deliverables, where templates can be found or how to raise an issue within the project.
- Project participants who look for a specific folder or document.
- New project participants: When a project partner includes new researchers in the project, this document provides an overview of the project structure.

2.4 Relationship with other deliverables

The management of the project data, and the quality assurance of project data, are described in the project's Data Management Plan, project deliverable D6.2 in **Error! Reference source not found.** The routines for disseminating results and communicating news are described in the project's

Dissemination and communication plan, project deliverable D5.2 in **Error! Reference source not found.**

3 Overview of the Man0EUvRE project

3.1 Project concept

The main objective of the Man0EUvRE project is to improve the framework and methodology for producing consistent national energy and climate plans across Europe. The project will do this by first developing clean energy transition scenarios towards 2050, including current policies like Fit-for-55 and REPowerEU, and the national energy and climate plans (NECPs) for the countries represented in the project. These scenarios will be used in an energy system model with a European dataset, and the outputs from the European simulation will be used as input for national or regional case studies. There are nine case studies in Man0EUvRE with different scopes. Their results will be compared with the NECP of the concerned countries or regions and fed back to the European energy system model dataset. The experience from the case studies will be used when the European energy system model dataset is updated. This will lead to learning about the clean energy transition, improve the future process of developing NECPs and align the NECPs with the European policies.

3.2 Project objectives

The overall aim of this project is to improve and coordinate energy system modelling across Europe and provide open scientific evidence and research-based results that facilitate ambitious emissions reductions for a clean energy transition (CET), while incorporating the measures suggested in REPowerEU and recent policy suggestions of the Fit for 55 package and the Net Zero Industrial act.

Subobjectives

- To develop robust pathways for the European energy system that meet climate targets towards net-zero greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions and consider current policies like the REPowerEU plan.
- To provide feedback and advice to the National Energy and Climate Plans (NECPs) of the individual EU countries.
- To improve the toolbox for conducting energy transition studies at both European and national level, which can support NECP generation, evaluation and future updates.
- To publish consistent energy system modelling datasets and scenario projections at both European and national level.
- To strengthen the coordination between national energy plans and EU-wide transition goals.

3.3 Participants and governance of Man0EUvRE

3.3.1 Project partners and voluntary partners

Error! Reference source not found. shows a list of project partners and their resources devoted to each work package in the Man0EUvRE project. VITO and VTT are self-financing project partners who do not receive funding for participation in the Man0EUvRE project, but who have coordinated their effort in Man0EUvRE with similar projects. The contact info for all project partners can be found in [contact info consortium and WP.xlsx](#).

Error! Reference source not found. shows the management structure of Man0EUvRE. The governance structure is described in[2].

Table 2: Project partners and the amount of person months devoted to the project by each partner.

Partner	WP1	WP2	WP3	WP4	WP5	WP6	SUM
SINTEF	0.2	0.2	0.9	0.2	0.4	13.8	15.7
TU Berlin	3	20	4.2	3	2	2	34.2
DLR	1	1	24.9	3.8	3	1	34.7
NTNU	4	2		3.5		0.5	10
LTU	0.2		7	0.2	0.6		8
EDF	2	4	8	4	1	1	20
UFZ	14.85	2.7	32.35	2.4	5.1	2	59.4
CIEMAT	5	2	24	8	2		41
E3M	2	2	24	11	8		47
KHAS	1	1	21	1	1		25
LNEG	1	1	13	4.3	1		20.3
IFE	0.2		7	0.2	0.6		8
SOLATOM	1		13	3	1		18
Greengoat	0.1		0.8	0.1			1
Power Circle	0.1		0.55	0.1			0.75
Hafslund Eco	0.4		0.4	0.2			1
Statkraft	0.4		0.4	0.2			1
Equinor	1	0.5	1	0.5			3
Gassco	0.4		0.4	0.2			1
VITO	2	2		2			6
VTT	0.2	0.2		0.1			0.5
Total PMs	40.05	38.6	182.9	48	25.7	20.3	355.55

Figure 1: The management structure of ManOEUVRE.

The work packages are:

- WP1: Scenario definition and parametrization
- WP2: Pan-European study / Top-down analysis
- WP3: Case studies / Bottom-up analysis
- WP4: Feedback to NECP
- WP5: Communication and dissemination
- WP6: Project management

3.3.2 General Assembly

The general assembly (GA) is the decision-making body of the consortium and consists of one representative of each project partner. Each member of the GA is deemed to be duly authorised to deliberate, negotiate, and decide on:

- Content, finances, and intellectual property rights
 - Changes to the consortium plan.
 - Additions, modifications, or withdrawal of Background in Attachment 1 in [ManOEUVRE consortium agreement final - signed.pdf](#) [2].
- Evolution of the consortium including appointment of new voluntary partners
- Breach, defaulting party status and litigation

In addition to these formal tasks, the GA will be used as a reference group on relevant results and deliverables, with the intention of reaching policy makers and maximising the impact of the project.

The GA is chaired by the project coordinator.

Information about the GA meetings, including minutes from the historical GA meetings, can be found in the [General Assembly meetings](#) folder.

3.3.3 Coordinator

The coordinator is the intermediary between the project partners by chairing the GA and the Management Support Team (MST). The coordinator is also responsible for collecting, verify consistency and submitting reports and other deliverables and specific requested documents to the CETP or the CETP Knowledge Community.

3.3.4 CETP Knowledge Community

The CETP Knowledge Community is a forum for knowledge exchange within the CETP projects. All activity within the knowledge community is initiated by the CETP management and the ManOEUVRE project is assigned tasks to participate in. The participation in the CETP Knowledge Community will be coordinated by the coordinator, although the Management Support Team is included in relevant communication. Participation in the CETP Knowledge Community by other project members will be coordinated by the ManOEUVRE coordinator. All information about presentation in and information from the CETP Knowledge Community is found in the [CETP Knowledge Community](#) folder.

3.3.5 Management Support Team

The MST consists of the WP leaders in the project and the coordinator. The coordinator chairs the MST meetings, which takes place every other week. The MST tasks are the daily management and coordination of the tasks in the project according to the workplans. The WP leaders are responsible for the coordination of the activities, tasks, milestones, and deliverables of the relevant WP. The status of each WP is discussed in the MST. The MST is also responsible for monitoring of risks and proposition of mitigation measures. All minutes from the MST meetings can be found in the [Management Support Team meetings](#) folder.

3.3.6 Stakeholder group

The ManOEUVRE project maintains a dynamic stakeholder group consisting of relevant stakeholders. To maximize the return on investment of the time spend by the stakeholders, they can choose between which activities they want to take part in.

Gathering stakeholders for the stakeholder list is done by the ManOEUVRE partners. The stakeholders giving their consent to be on the stakeholder list are registered in the [Stakeholder matrix.xlsx](#).

3.4 Timeline

The ManOEUVRE project started in December 2023 and has a duration of 3 years. It will finish in December 2026. The project timeline is shown in **Error! Reference source not found.**. The Gantt chart producing this timeline is found in [Timeline gantt chart.xlsx](#). A more detailed Gantt chart showing the dependencies in the project is shown in **Error! Reference source not found.**

Year	23	2024												2025												2026																							
Month	12	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11													
WP1		M1.1												M1.2																																			
Task 1.1		D1.1																																															
Task 1.2				D1.2																																													
Task 1.3																																																	
WP2					M2.1												M2.2												M2.3, M2.4																				
Task 2.1																																																	
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WP3		M3.1												M3.2																																			
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Task 3.9																										D3.1																							
WP4																										M4.1																							
Task 4.1																																																	
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Task 4.3																																					D4.2												
WP5		M5.1																																															
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WP6		M6.1																																															
Task 6.1		D6.1																																															
Task 6.2																																																	
Task 6.3		D6.2																																															

Figure 2: Timeline for the Man0EUvRE project.

Figure 3: Gantt chart showing project dependencies, collected from the WP3 workplan.

3.5 Deliverables

Table 3: List of deliverables for Man0EUvRE.

No	Deliverable name	WP	Lead	Date
D1.1	Journal paper: Energy Transition Pathways to realize REPowerEU: A review on trends, challenges, and opportunities	1	NTNU	M7
D1.2	Report and data sets: Description of data inputs and modelling assumptions used for the Scenarios	1	NTNU	M9
D2.1	Report on European energy system futures, focusing on Fit for 55 and REPowerEU	2	TU Berlin	M15
D2.2	“European Vision” - Summary report of insights gained and updated model results for the integrated European case	2	TU Berlin	M33
D2.3	Final model version of GENeSYS-MOD including input and output datasets	2	TU Berlin	M33
D3.1	Executive summaries of case studies	3	UFZ, CS leads	M24
D4.1	NECP Man0EUvRE vision: analyses of the NECPs of the considered country	4	EDF	M30
D4.2	NECP Methodology for enhancing the NECP process by using Man0EUvRE tools.	4	EDF	M36
D5.1	One start-up workshop with relevant project partners and need owners on scenario generation and best advice to NECPs	5	NTNU, EDF	M3
D5.2	Dissemination and communication plan	5	DLR	M6
D5.3	Dissemination activity report, also referring to activities located in other work packages incl. case studies, to be updated every year	5	DLR	M13, M25, M36
D5.4	National dissemination workshops of WP3 case studies (partners with lead in case studies), presenting the case study results to national authorities and policy makers	5	DLR, CS leads	M30
D5.5	Final Project report	5	SINTEF	M36
D5.6	One final workshop with relevant project partners and need owners on scenario generation and best advice to NECPs	5	NTNU, EDF, SINTEF	M36
D6.1	Project Management Plan including Quality Plan	6	SINTEF	M6
D6.2	Data Management Plan	6	SINTEF	M6

3.6 Milestones

Table 4: List of milestones for Man0EUvRE.

No	Milestone name	WP	Means of verification	Date
M1.1	Man0EUvRE Scenarios Defined in Dialogue with Stakeholders and the Consortium	1	Workshop presentation	M6
M1.2	Input data and modelling assumptions available for all scenarios	1	D1.1, D1.2	M9
M2.1	Developed model and dataset have been used for the initial pan-European study	2	D2.1	M12
M2.2	1 st iteration of Pan-European energy pathways has been completed	2	D2.1	M15
M2.3	Quantified final European pathways, combining both national and European-level insights	2	D2.2	M33
M2.4	Final modal and full data set, published publicly	2	D2.3	M33
M3.1	Incorporating GENeSYS-MOD outputs into case study models, formats as data tables circulated to case study partners	3	Project meetings	M16
M3.2	All 9 case studies have delivered their results to the pan-European study and uploaded models and data to repository	3	Repository upload, D2.2	M24
M4.1	The NECP vs Manoeuvre case studies comparisons have been presented and discussed in workshops with national and EU representatives	4	D5.4	M32
M5.1	The project website is online	5	Website launch	M3
M6.1	Data exchange format is defined for internal use	6	D6.2	M6

3.7 Work packages

Man0EUvRE is divided into 6 work packages (WPs), led by 6 different Man0EUvRE partners. Each WP leader has made a workplan for their WP. The workplans are tools intended to help structuring the project and be detailed enough to lead on. In the MST meetings the WP leaders discuss the status of the workplans and facilitate decision making to ensure progress in the project. The MST will follow progress and the WP-leaders must lead on the workplans. The workplans are living documents that are discussed and approved in the MST.

The work package work plans can be found here:

- [WP1 Plan_V01_11_01_2024.docx](#).
- [WP2 Plan.docx](#).
- [WP3 Man0EUvRE Project Plan-Detailed.pdf](#)
- [WP4 Plan.docx](#).
- [WP5 Plan_240111.docx](#).

- [WP6 plan.docx](#).

The case studies are based in WP3, and work plans for the case studies can be found here:

- Case study 1: Green H2 and thermal energy storage in Spain, see [CS1 - CIEMAT](#).
- Case study 2: Modelling Norwegian and Swedish energy export to facilitate the European low-carbon transition using TIMES models, see [CS2 - IFE](#).
- Case study 3: Global competitiveness and the energy demand of the energy-intensive industry, see [CS3 - DLR](#).
- Case study 4: The role of growing demand in refinancing renewables, see [CS4 - DLR](#).
- Case study 5: Soft-linking BENOPTex and GENeSYS-MOD, see [CS5 - UFZ](#).
- Case study 6: Integrating electricity and gas network supported by energy storage and power conversion processes, see [CS6 - KHAS](#).
- Case study 7: Greece as a renewable energy hub, see [CS7 - E3M](#).
- Case study 8: Green transition in France, see [CS8 - EDF](#).
- Case study 9: Power market modelling: Spain and Portugal, see [CS9 - LNEG](#).

4 Quality Assurance

To ensure that milestones and deliverables are reached in due time and with high quality, a set of routines are described. Additionally, templates are made available to ensure that reports, presentations and progress reports follow the necessary guidelines set by the CETP management. This chapter is based on experience from earlier EU projects coordinated by SINTEF Energi AS[3], [4] and is a living document that will be adapted if needed.

4.1 Templates

To comply with the requirements from the CETP management, templates are made available on SharePoint for the ManOEUVRE project group. The written and the visual templates contain an acknowledgement as required by the CETP management, the CETP logo, the EU emblem, and the logos of the relevant funding agencies.

4.1.1 Reports

A report template in Word will be made available for all project partners. It will contain a front page and reference pages identifying the document, revision control, quality assurance and the general status of the document. As required by the CETP management, the template will contain an acknowledgement with details about the CETP programme. The template will contain a generic table of contents including an executive summary of the report, a list of acronyms, an introduction and a reference list. The report template will also contain the ManOEUVRE logo and the CETP logo, the EU emblem and the logos of the relevant funding agencies.

4.1.2 Presentations

A PowerPoint presentation template will be made available for all project partners. It will contain a front page, a regular slide format, and an end page, with the ManOEUVRE logo and the CETP logo, the EU emblem and the logos of the relevant funding agencies, as well as an acknowledgement with details about the CETP programme.

4.1.3 Progress reports

The project will deliver annual progress reports to the CETP knowledge community for the first and second year, and a final report for the third year, that include milestones and deliverables. These progress reports will follow a template specified by the CETP knowledge community and will be reported through the DISCCO portal.

National or regional reporting will follow national or regional procedures and rules and will be conducted by the respective partners.

4.2 Publications

All publications must contain an acknowledgment as required by the CETP management. As specified in the Consortium Agreement 8.4.2.1, all ManOEUVRE parties must be notified of the final draft of all publications within due time.

4.3 Milestones

A ManOEUVRE milestone has a chronological placement in the project plan and is intended to gather the project as a whole and be a checkpoint for a change from one project phase to the next. All ManOEUVRE milestones are specified in **Error! Reference source not found.** with a due date specified as the last of the given month. The Coordinator specifies whether each milestone was achieved in the annual progress report and through reporting on the DISCCO portal.

To ensure a high level of quality in the project work leading to the ManOEUVRE milestones, the following system is used:

- Each milestone has a lead partner. The lead partner appoints one person to ensure that the milestone is reached in due time and that the milestone contributes to the ManOEUVRE project objectives.
- The responsibility for coordination of the accomplishment and quality of the milestone is the lead of the WP where the milestone is placed.
- As soon as a milestone is reached, the management support team is informed by the responsible WP lead.
- When notified, the Coordinator will report in the DISCCO portal that the milestone was reached.

4.4 Deliverables

A ManOEUVRE deliverable is the formal output of the project and has a chronological placement in the project plan. The deliverables in ManOEUVRE are:

- Report:
 - Description of data inputs and modelling assumptions used for the ManOEUVRE scenarios,
 - Report on European energy system futures, focusing on Fit for 55 and REPowerEU,
 - “European Vision” – Summary report of insights gained and updated model results for the integrated European case,
 - Executive summaries of case studies,
 - NECP ManOEUVRE vision: analyses of the NECPs of the considered countries,
 - NECP Methodology and toolbox implementing a methodology for enhancing the NECP process by using ManOEUVRE tools,

- Dissemination activity report, to be updated every year,
- Final project report,
- Journal paper
 - Energy Transition Pathways to realize REPowerEU: A review on trends, challenges and opportunities,
- Model code and datasets
 - Data inputs for the Pan-European study,
 - Final model version of GENeSYS-MOD including input and output datasets,
- Minutes of workshops
 - Start-up workshop with relevant project partners and stakeholders on scenario generation and best advice to NECPs,
 - National dissemination workshops of WP3 case studies, presenting the case study results to national authorities and policy makers,
 - Final workshop with relevant project partners and stakeholders on scenario generation and best advice to NECPs.
- Plans:
 - Data Management Plan
 - Project Management Plan
 - Dissemination and Communication Plan

All ManOEUVRE deliverables are specified in **Error! Reference source not found.** with a due date specified as the last of the given month. The Coordinator specifies whether the deliverable was achieved in the annual progress report and through reporting on the DISCCO portal.

To ensure a high level of quality in the project work leading to the ManOEUVRE deliverables, the following system is used:

- Each deliverable has a lead partner responsible for the deliverable. The partner appoints two roles filled by one person or more people to follow up on the deliverable:
 - The first role shall ensure that the deliverable is reached in due time to enable a sufficient quality assurance, that the deliverable is of high scientific quality and that the deliverable contributes to the ManOEUVRE project objectives. **The deliverable must be complete and ready for a final quality assurance one month prior to the official due date.**
 - The second role shall verify the quality of the research leading to the deliverable. This person/group carrying out this role must be approved by the management support team before the quality assurance is carried out and cannot be someone who was involved in the development of the deliverable. The quality verification of the deliverable will be conducted according to the routines of the quality assurance responsible person's institute and must ensure that the deliverable is according to the objectives and that the template for deliverables is followed, if applicable.
- The responsibility for coordination of the accomplishment and quality of the deliverable is the lead of the WP where the deliverable is placed.

- Upon disagreement on the quality of a deliverable, the question will be treated in the Management Support Team.
- As soon as a deliverable is reached, the management support team is informed by the responsible WP lead and can then approve the deliverable.
- Once the management support team has approved the deliverable, the Coordinator will submit the deliverable in the DISCCO portal.

5 Risk Management

One of the tasks of the Management Support Team is the monitoring of risks and proposition of mitigation measures. **Error! Reference source not found.** contains the risks and mitigation measures identified for the ManOEUVRE project, where the first version was prepared for the project application.

Each partner must report to their respective WP leader and to the coordinator if they encounter new risks or changes in risks. In the status report submitted by the WP leaders every six months, a risk assessment is included. If there are problems or delays, the respective WP leader or coordinator must consult the MST, which will take actions or consult the GA to implement mitigation measures.

Table 5: Identified risks and preventive or mitigation measures.

#	Risk description and preventive/mitigation measures	WP	Probability	Severity
1	Pan-European pathway scenarios may not be prepared on time	1,2	low	Medium
	Collect information from sources in parallel, or limited or already available versions can be used. Scenario quantification and implementation starts early, WP1			
	Status M6: We have made a good start, scenarios are under preparation, parametrization is still missing. OK. Risk measures are the same. Status M12: Status M18: Status M24: Status M30:			
2	Upscaling case study results proves to be more difficult than expected	3	Medium	Medium
	Chances for optimal upscaling results improves by discussing solutions early in WP3			
	Status M6: Will be discussed in a WP3 meeting in the beginning of the next reporting period. Standardization preparations have been made. Storylines of scenarios are clear to the partners. Status M12: Status M18: Status M24: Status M30:			
3	Increase of the computational effort in the models due to developments	3	medium	low

	Early test of computing times, algorithm optimizations and/or solver change. If necessary, adaptation or simplification of the process can take place.			
	Status M6: OK. Following the result expectations. Status M12: Status M18: Status M24: Status M30:			
4	Loss of relevant research competence, due to e.g., sickness or leaves.	all	Medium	Medium
	Reach out to other institutes and universities nationally and in the ETSAP community for support. All partners are well-experienced and of sufficient size and can handle such issues when they emerge.			
	Status M6: No such incident has been handled in this reporting period. Risk assessment stays the same. E3M received their funding late, but it does not affect their effort in the project. Status M12: Status M18: Status M24: Status M30:			
5	Difficulties of capturing all aspects in case studies due to the project interdisciplinarity.	3	medium	medium
	The case study and system boundary should be accurately defined. Case studies should be transparent regarding their limitations in the reports.			
	Status M6: We need to make sure that we do not promise more than we can keep, and that the promised topics are covered at least qualitatively. Status M12: Status M18: Status M24: Status M30:			
6	Difficulties in soft linking the models	3	Low	medium
	Start with analysis of all involved models and input data formats. Advice from resources outside of ManOEUVRE could be requested. Simplifications of the soft-linking process if problems persist.			
	Status M6: The IAMC format is chosen as data exchange format and knowledge about this is high in the consortium. Probability is downgraded to low. Status M12: Status M18: Status M24: Status M30:			
7	Difficulties in assessing markets and NECP data	3,4	Very low	High

	Identification of requested data upfront and of relevant stakeholders. Adaptation of model's inputs if necessary. Most data are already available to the modelling teams.			
	Status M6: WP3 has engaged a Ph.D. that increases capacity for finding the right info in the NECP's Status M12: Status M18: Status M24: Status M30:			
8	Difficulties with alignment of energy models' output with national policies in NECPs in order to suggest improvement of NECPs.	3,4	medium	medium
	Introduction of constraints in models, and adaptation of reference NECPs. Start from the most important indicators and progress to more detailed ones.			
	Status M6: We need to continue to consider this in the work with scenarios. The text has been revised. Status M12: Status M18: Status M24: Status M30:			
9	Economics of thermal storage design by SOLATOM.	3	medium	medium
	Great effort has been used to reduce the O&M costs of the design. If the technology underperforms, the data obtained could still be used to model the scenarios in TIMES-SINERGIA.			
	Status M6: We continue to monitor the risk. Status M12: Status M18: Status M24: Status M30:			
10	Integration of new energy infrastructure into the case studies	3	Low	High
	Stakeholder dialogue to identify the important and relevant energy infrastructure projects to be included.			
	Status M6: Jour Fixe-meetings in WP3 that have already started. We keep the communication with the stakeholders. Status M12: Status M18: Status M24: Status M30:			
11	Description.....		?	?
	Mitigation.....			
	Status M6:			

	Status M12: Status M18: Status M24: Status M30:			
12	Description.....		?	?
	Mitigation.....			
	Status M6: Status M12: Status M18: Status M24: Status M30:			
13	Description....		?	?
	Mitigation.....			
	Status M6: Status M12: Status M18: Status M24: Status M30:			

6 Reporting

ManOEUVRE is a CETP 2022 project and is subject to annual reporting the first and second year, and a final report in the third year, to the CETP management through the DISSCO portal. Additionally, national or regional reporting follows national or regional procedures and rules for the respective partners.

6.1 Annual and final reports

The annual reports to the DISSCO reporting portal will contain:

- General data,
- Work process,
- Dissemination and communication,
- Thematic and cross-cutting challenges,
- Achievements, findings, impact & exploitation

The annual and final report will follow a template provided by the CETP management. The first annual report is due in the end of 2024 or the beginning of 2025.

6.2 Financial reporting

Part of the annual and final reporting to the CETP management will contain changes in the project budget or used resources, thus all partners must provide the coordinator with necessary information.

The funding agreements are between the respective partners and their funding agencies and are not governed by the project management.

7 Communication and information tools and procedures

7.1 Internal communication

ManOEUVRE uses an email alias for communication to all project partners. This email address can be used by anyone, and everyone on the list will receive any email sent to the email address. The list is maintained by SINTEF. The email address is:

manOeuvre_participants@SINTEF.onmicrosoft.com

ManOEUVRE uses SharePoint for internal file sharing and storing. The following information will be found on the ManOEUVRE SharePoint workroom:

- GA invitations and minutes
- MST minutes and meeting slides
- Drafts and final deliverables
- Templates
- Minutes from other relevant meetings
- CETP Knowledge Community materials
- Illustrations
- List of stakeholders
- The Consortium Agreement

All partners shall have access to a shared SharePoint folder and may upload to or download from this folder. Any request for access or rights to the SharePoint can be directed to the project coordinator.

7.2 External communication

External communication is described in deliverable D5.2, the Dissemination and communication plan. The external communication includes the project webpage <https://manOeuvre.eu/> and the LinkedIn page <https://www.linkedin.com/company/manOeuvre/>.

8 References

- [1] 'DESCA for Horizon Europe model Consortium Agreement version 1.1'.
- [2] 'Consortium agreement ManOEUVRE, Version 1 - 16.11.2023'.
- [3] 'HORIZON 101118123 OpenMod4Africa'.
- [4] 'H2020 835896 Open ENTRANCE'.